

QUANTUM COMPUTING APPLIED IN ELECTRICAL CIRCUITS

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Abstract – In order to study the complex quantities of an electric circuit, this article presents the development of the theoretical concepts of electromagnetism through Maxwell's Equations, to understand the resistive, capacitive and inductive nature of the components. In addition, a Python programming code was made that analyzes the parameters of an alternating current RLC circuit, and calculates the amplitude and phase values of the quantities through Microsoft's Azure Quantum software, a quantum computer specialized in developing complex calculations based on the principles of quantum mechanics.

Keywords: Maxwell's equations; Microsoft Azure; Electrical Circuit's Theory; Quantum Computing.

INTRODUCTION

In 1864, based on the studies of Michael Faraday, the British physicist James Clark Maxwell unified the observable electrical and magnetic phenomenon's and established the connections of the theory of electrical circuits through the arrangement of Maxwell's equations, and with this he was the first researcher to find through mathematical calculations the speed of electromagnetic waves. By the end of the XIX century, Maxwell's equations were the most advanced in scientific circles, and contributed to subsequent studies. It was then that Max Planck and Albert Einstein, with their postulates on Black body Radiation, the Theory of Relativity and the Photoelectric Effect, which opened to the development of the concepts of quantum mechanics in the XX century. In 1980, the American physicist, Richard Feynman, and the Russian mathematical, Yuri Manin, proposed the principles of the quantum computing, using statistical analysis and the principle of superposition.

These days, Google and IBM develop research's, build and sell quantum computers. Its principle of operation is in the so-called qubits, which assume the state of 0, 1 and the superposition (assumes 0 and 1 at the same time). In addition, it is expected to use quantum computing in processes in industry due to its powerful computational processing, among some applications of quantum computing are: the simulation of the behavior of atoms and molecules in order to adapt and synthesize new medicines, Cybersecurity and password cracking, and also in the statistical analysis of industrial plants through the data collected by plant sensing, to provide the best predictive maintenance. That said, the present article demonstrates the application of quantum computing in the analysis and sizing of electrical circuits, in which

[1] presents the basis of quantum theory, [2] and [3] establishes the connection of Maxwell's equations with circuit theory, and also in [3] it is rescued the example of RLC circuit that was modeled in a programming code and submitted to Azure Quantum software [4], to gather data and present the results of quantum computing efficiency.

DEVELOPMENT

Maxwell's equations for electromagnetism are contained in Gauss's Laws, for electricity (i) and for magnetism (ii), Faraday's Law (iii) and Ampère-Maxwell's Law (iv):

$$\begin{aligned} (i) = \nabla \cdot D &= 0, & (iii) = \nabla \cdot E &= \frac{-\partial B}{\partial t} \\ (ii) = \nabla \cdot B &= 0, & (iv) = \nabla \cdot H &= \frac{\partial D}{\partial t} \end{aligned}$$

They relate the quantities that configure and originate the electric and magnetic fields, but also establish their inseparable relationship, which results in the composition of the electromagnetic wave. In Figure [1] is presented the arrangement of an electromagnetic wave, which is composed of the electric field (E) and the magnetic field (B), orthogonal to each other.

Figure [1] – Representation of the electromagnetic wave.

These fields have a sine waveform, which is widely present in nature, and determines a complete cycle in radians, from 0 to 2π , in a given period of time, in seconds. In the case of figure [1] it is possible to see that the wave begins and ends from crest to crest, but it can also be analyzed from valley to valley or with beginning and end on the axis of propagation c . The wave also has a frequency (ν), measured in hertz, which varies from one medium to the other due to the permittivity (ϵ) and permeability (μ) of the wave propagation medium, which can be identified by treating Maxwell's (iii) and (iv) equations. In addition, the higher the frequency, the shorter the period (T), due to its inverse property, that is, when a wave transitions from one medium to another, the frequency of the same decreases or increases worth the inverse par to its period.

Figure [2] – Phasorial representation of the behavior of the electromagnetic wave.

Figure [2] presents an illustration of what happens when a wave transitions from one medium to another. One can analyze permittivity and permeability as an intrinsic characteristic of a material. By analyzing the speed of propagation of an electromagnetic wave in a vacuum, obtains:

$$c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} = 3,00 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$$

Through the Law of Reflection and Refraction (Snell's Law), it becomes evident the complex nature of the electromagnetic wave, that is, its amplitude and argument (or phase):

$$k_I \sin \theta_I = k_R \sin \theta_R = k_T \sin \theta_T$$

The previous form describes the behavior that an electromagnetic wave assumes when transiting through space. If it does not have a separation between two spaces, the wave crosses space without changing its amplitude and frequency. But when there is a separation between more than one space, depending on the difficulty of transition of the incidence plan, the

propagation index of the incident wave is different from the transmitted wave ($k_I \neq k_T$), that is, the intensity of propagation and transmission of the wave decreases and there is a change of direction of the transmission vector in relation to the incidence ($\sin \theta_I \neq \sin \theta_T$); For example: from air to water. The wave can undergo a refraction (transmits part of the energy but loses a portion due to the difficulty caused by the resistance of the second space), a reflection (partial or total, the last being when it returns entirely to the space of incidence of the wave due to the high impediment of the other medium) or the complete transfer of energy.

One of the mathematical tools Maxwell developed was phasorial analysis to help understand the complex nature of the waveform. It was defined that the X and Y axes of the Cartesian plane represent the real and imaginary values, respectively. These are the foundations of circuit theory, which uses the complex numbers to calculate the amplitude of the wave and its lag modulated by a sine function, either in polar or Cartesian (rectangular) form.

$$Z = \text{Real}(R) \pm j\text{Complex}(C)$$

The value in the use of complex numbers is visible at the moment when calculating the characteristic quantities of an electromagnetic circuit, by using the rectangular form to affect the sum and subtraction, due to the separation between the real part and the imaginary part (preceded by the j), and the product and the ratio in the polar form, to facilitate the sum or subtraction of phases.

$$P = \text{Amplitude} \angle \text{Phase}$$

Quantum Theory says that what is seen in the micro universe is reflected in the macro universe, that is, through Maxwell's equations it is possible to understand what are the factors in the micro universe ($\epsilon\mu$) are reflecting in the macro. The difficulty of an electromagnetic wave transiting from one material to another depends on whether or not it overcomes opposition to its passage. Therefore, at this point, the concept of resistance of a material and its conductivity (σ) is established. The material now has a dielectric constant that allows the passage of electric current (J). When the material is a good conductor, the electric charges that pass through it produce an electric field and consequently a voltage. Thus, by manipulating Maxwell's (iv) equation, one arrives at Ohm's Law:

$$E = R \cdot I$$

Where the current and voltage are proportional physical quantities, and inversely proportional to the resistance. However, an electrical circuit is not only composed of purely resistive components, but there are also other components that, due to the double

nature of the electromagnetic wave, store E and B. Consequently, the circuits have an inductive or capacitive nature, and the opposition to the current passage is called impedance (Z), given in ohms, formed by the real and imaginary component (capacitive or inductive reactance). It's inverse, the Admittance (Y), is formed by the conductance (real) and susceptance (complex) in siemens. The function of the components of an electrical circuit are: the resistor represents a real quantity (without lag) and does not provide delay in current or voltage, which remain in phase. The capacitor stores electric fields inside mechanically, that is, it causes a delay of the voltage in relation to the current, while the inductor (coil) stores magnetic fields, which delay the current in relation to the voltage. The most common circuits are RL (resistor and inductor), RC (resistor and capacitor) and RLC.

To calculate the impedance or total admittance of a circuit, one must consider the topology of the circuit. When the circuit is in series, the current passing through the components is the same, but the voltage on them is different. But when the circuit is in parallel the voltage is the same on the components, but the current is different. Both must respect Kirchhoff's Law of Currents and Tensions. The impedance and total admittance are of a series circuit with the following and forms:

$$Z_T = Z_1 + Z_2 + Z_3 + \dots + Z_n$$

$$Y_T = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{Y_1} + \frac{1}{Y_2} + \frac{1}{Y_3} + \dots + \frac{1}{Y_n}}$$

The impedance and total admittance of a series circuit are calculated with the following formulas:

$$Z_T = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{Z_1} + \frac{1}{Z_2} + \frac{1}{Z_3} + \dots + \frac{1}{Z_n}}$$

$$Y_T = Y_1 + Y_2 + Y_3 + \dots + Y_n$$

With circuit theory established, we resorted to using Azure Quantum software, made available by IBM and Microsoft, to perform the experiment. It gives a small portion of a quantum computer, in which the simulation data arrives through the cloud, for the execution of projects and programming, without the need for download or computer requirements, only an access to internet connection and a Microsoft account [4]. The software provides a command interface that interacts with the Python or Q# programming language, where any type of program that would be made on a classical computer can be used. The Q# language comes from Microsoft Azure itself and is

only available to it. The experiment recommended three steps: the first was to select an alternating current (AC) RLC circuit, available in [2] and illustrated in figure [4].

Figure [3] – RLC circuit series in AC with the values of the impedances.

The second step was the develop of the code, available in figures [4] and [5] that reproduces the theoretical principles of electrical circuits and adjusted to work for the topology of figure [3]. Finally, it was about collecting the data provided by the quantum computer for analysis.

```
import math
import cmath
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
amplitude = 0
def impedancia_resistor(R):
    return R
def impedancia_bobina(L, f, defasagem):
    j = complex(0, 1) # Unidade imaginaria
    return j * 2 * cmath.pi * f * L * cmath.exp(1j * math.radians(defasagem))
def impedancia_capacitor(C, f, defasagem):
    j = complex(0, 1) # Unidade imaginaria
    return 1 / (j * 2 * cmath.pi * f * C * cmath.exp(1j * math.radians(defasagem)))
def admittancia(Z):
    return 1 / Z
def impedancia_total_serie(Z1, Z2):
    return Z1 + Z2
def admittancia_total_serie(Y1, Y2):
    return Y1 + Y2
def impedancia_total_paralelo(Z1, Z2):
    return 1 / (1 / Z1 + 1 / Z2)
def admittancia_total_paralelo(Y1, Y2):
    return Y1 + Y2
def calcular_defasagem(Z):
    return cmath.degrees(cmath.phase(Z))
def calcular_senoid(frequencia, amplitude, fase, tempo):
    return amplitude * np.sin(2 * np.pi * frequencia * tempo + np.deg2rad(fase))
R = float(input("Digite o valor da resistencia (em ohms): "))
L = float(input("Digite o valor do indutor (em henrys): "))
C = float(input("Digite o valor do capacitor (em farads): "))
frequencia = float(input("Digite a frequencia da fonte (em hertz): "))
tipo_circuito = input("Digite 'S' para serie ou 'P' para paralelo: ").upper()
tipo_calculo = input("Digite 'I' para tensao ou 'C' para corrente: ").upper()
if tipo_calculo == 'I':
    amplitude = float(input("Digite a amplitude da tensao (em volts): "))
elif tipo_calculo == 'C':
    amplitude = float(input("Digite a amplitude da corrente (em amperes): "))
Z_R = impedancia_resistor(R)
Z_L = impedancia_bobina(L, frequencia, 90)
Z_C = impedancia_capacitor(C, frequencia, -90)
Y_R = admittancia(Z_R)
Y_L = admittancia(Z_L)
Y_C = admittancia(Z_C)
if tipo_circuito == 'S':
    Z_total = impedancia_total_serie(Z_R, impedancia_total_paralelo(Z_L, Z_C))
    Y_total = admittancia_total_serie(Y_R, admittancia_total_paralelo(Y_L, Y_C))
    I = complex(amplitude, 0) # Corrente em serie
    V = Z_total * I # Tensao em serie
elif tipo_circuito == 'P':
    Z_total = impedancia_total_paralelo(Z_R, impedancia_total_serie(Z_L, Z_C))
    Y_total = admittancia_total_paralelo(Y_R, admittancia_total_serie(Y_L, Y_C))
    V = complex(amplitude, 0) # Tensao em paralelo
    I = Y_total * V # Corrente em paralelo
else:
    pass
```

Figure [4] – First part of the code in Python of the RLC circuit.

```
print("Escolha de circuito invalida. Use 'S' para série ou 'P' para paralelo.")
exit()
tempo = np.linspace(0, 0.1, 1000) # 1000 pontos de 0 a 0.1 segundos
Z_senoide = calcular_senoide(frequencia, abs(Z_total), cmath.phase(Z_total), tempo)
I_senoide = calcular_senoide(frequencia, abs(I), cmath.phase(I), tempo)
V_senoide = calcular_senoide(frequencia, abs(V), 0, tempo)
Y_senoide = calcular_senoide(frequencia, abs(Y_total), cmath.phase(Y_total), tempo)
print("\nDados coletados:")
print("Resistência (ohms): {R}")
print("Indutor (henrys): {L}")
print("Defasagem do indutor (graus): 90°")
print("Capacitor (farads): {C}")
print("Defasagem do capacitor (graus): -90°")
print("Frequência (hertz): {frequencia}")
print("Configuração do circuito: {Série if tipo_circuito == 'S' else Paralelo}")
if tipo_calculo == "T":
    print("Amplitude da tensão (volts): {amplitude}")
elif tipo_calculo == "C":
    print("Amplitude da corrente (amperes): {amplitude}")
print("\nResultados:")
print("Impedância Total: {Z_total}")
print("Admitância Total: {Y_total}")
if tipo_calculo == "T":
    print("Tensão: {V}")
elif tipo_calculo == "C":
    print("Corrente: {I}")
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
plt.subplot(2, 1, 1)
plt.plot(tempo, Z_senoide, label='Impedância (Z)')
if tipo_calculo == "T":
    plt.plot(tempo, V_senoide, label='Tensão (V)')
elif tipo_calculo == "C":
    plt.plot(tempo, I_senoide, label='Corrente (I)')
plt.xlabel('Tempo (s)')
plt.ylabel('Amplitude')
plt.title('Senoídes das Impedâncias, Corrente e Tensão')
plt.legend()
plt.subplot(2, 1, 2)
plt.plot(tempo, Y_senoide, label='Admitância (Y)')
plt.xlabel('Tempo (s)')
plt.ylabel('Amplitude')
plt.title('Senoídes das Admitâncias')
plt.legend()
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Figure [5] – Second part of the Python code of the RLC circuit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First, a software program was executed for the RLC circuit in AC series, which presented the data available in Figure [6]. The graph in Figure [7], although it does not show the lag in each impedance, efficiently displays the different amplitudes between each component.

```
Dados coletados:
Resistência (ohms): 8.0
Indutor (henrys): 0.004
Defasagem do indutor (graus): 90°
Capacitor (farads): 0.0001
Defasagem do capacitor (graus): -90°
Frequência (hertz): 159.15
Configuração do circuito: Série
Amplitude da corrente (amperes): 12.0
```

Figure [6] – Result of the calculation of the RLC circuit in series.

```
Resultados:
Impedância Total: (1.3338164391217635+4.081860180179118e-16j)
Admitância Total: (-0.02501087066799207-9.185516630043201e-18j)
Corrente: (12+0j)
```


Figure [7] – Graph of the calculation of the RLC circuit in series

Likewise, the data of the parallel AC RLC circuit in Figure [8] and its respective graph, available in Figure [9], were calculated. When comparing the results, it is noticed that the values of impedance and total admittance (in blue) remained the same in both tests, while the current amplitude (in orange) was higher in the series circuit, shown in figure [7], but

lower than the impedance amplitude in the parallel circuit, presented in figure [9]. The values of the arguments of the total impedance and admittance are in phase, however, when analyzing individually the phase values of the resistor, inductor and capacitor, both will be outdated in relation to the other, as can be seen in figures [6] and [8].

```
Dados coletados:
Resistência (ohms): 8.0
Indutor (henrys): 0.004
Defasagem do indutor (graus): 90°
Capacitor (farads): 0.0001
Defasagem do capacitor (graus): -90°
Frequência (hertz): 159.15
Configuração do circuito: Paralelo
Amplitude da corrente (amperes): 12.0
```

Figure [8] – Result of the calculation of the RLC circuit in parallel

```
Resultados:
Impedância Total: (3.4287134083966677-1.199666425437848e-16j)
Admitância Total: (-0.02501087066799207-9.185516630043201e-18j)
Corrente: (-0.3001304480159048-1.102261995605184e-16j)
```


Figure [9] – Graph of the calculation of the RLC circuit in parallel.

In addition, it was remarkable how quickly the quantum computer executed the program, taking milliseconds for the result to be obtained, and this is due to the probabilistic nature of the computer, assuming the best state and adapting the possible answers to approach the most ideal, dealing with calculations such as complex numbers (compared to the conventional computer, that would take a longer processing time). This is done through the interference method by using the Schrödinger equation (differential equation with complex numbers). Therefore, the previous program demonstrated the quantum computer engaging the function of analysis and sizing of electrical circuits, and this, would allow an improvement in the industrial sector, such as in the sensing of plants, occasional energy losses and predictive analysis of general failures.

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